

**TRADE RELATIONS OF THE KHANATES OF BUKHARA, KOKAND AND KHIVA
IN THE 19TH CENTURY: DOMESTIC AND EXTERNAL DIRECTIONS**

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Annotation. This article analyzes the formation, stages and directions of trade relations between the Bukhara and Kokand khanates in the 19th century. The article focuses on the internal and external trade network, caravan routes, market activities, and economic relations between merchants. In particular, foreign trade relations with Russia, China, and other neighboring countries, the tax and customs system, and the features of trade policy are widely covered. The study also examines the economic competition between the Bukhara and Kokand khanates, forms of cooperation, and issues of ensuring the security of trade routes. The article is written based on historical sources and archival materials and serves to study the general state of the Central Asian trade system in the 19th century.

Keywords. Kokand Khanate, 19th century, Trade relations, Internal trade, Foreign trade, Caravan routes, Markets, Merchants, Trade policy, Trade with Russia, Trade with China, Tax and customs system, Trade caravans.

**XIX ASRDA BUXORO, QO'QON VA XIVA XONLIKLARINING SAVDO
ALOQALARI: ICHKI VA TASHQI YO'NALISHLAR**

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Annatsiya. Ushbu maqolada XIX asrda Buxoro va Qo'qon xonliklari o'rtasidagi savdo aloqalarining shakllanishi, rivojlanish bosqichlari va yo'nalishlari tahlil qilingan. Maqolada ichki va tashqi savdo tarmog'i, karvon yo'llari, bozorlar faoliyati hamda savdogarlar o'rtasidagi iqtisodiy munosabatlarga e'tibor qaratiladi. Ayniqsa, Rossiya, Xitoy va boshqa qo'shni davlatlar bilan olib borilgan tashqi savdo aloqalari, soliqlar va boj tizimi, savdo siyosatining xususiyatlari keng yoritilgan. Tadqiqot davomida Buxoro va Qo'qon xonliklarining o'zaro iqtisodiy raqobati, hamkorlik shakllari va savdo yo'llari xavfsizligini ta'minlash masalalari ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqola tarixiy manbalar va arxiv materiallariga tayanib yozilgan bo'lib, XIX asrdagi Markaziy Osiyo savdo tizimining umumiy holatini o'rganishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Qo'qon xonligi, XIX asr, Savdo aloqalari, Ichki savdo, Tashqi savdo, Karvon yo'llari, Bozorlar, Savdogarlar, Savdo siyosati, Rossiya bilan savdo, Xitoy bilan savdo, Soliq va boj tizimi, Savdo karvonlari

The Khanate of Khiva and the Emirate of Bukhara were among the largest states in Central Asia, and their neighborly relations were based mainly on political, military, economic and cultural aspects. Since ancient times, Khiva and Bukhara were located on strategic trade routes and were

economically interconnected. The trade caravans passing through the Silk Road were of great importance for both khanates.

The Khiva Khanate traded with the Bukhara Emirate by water and land routes. In this regard, several cities were brought by land routes.

The shortest distance of the caravan route from Khiva to Bukhara was 335 versts, and the main route of this route passed along the routes of Azaris, Kokertli, Uchochok, Shorbulak, Agrabod, Chorgoshi, Bukhara. The main route of the caravan route from Bukhara to Khiva branched after reaching Kukertli and continued to Khiva in two directions.

The first: from Kukertli to Urgench -144 versts, from Urgench to Khiva -24 versts. The second route: from Kukertli to Azaris -72 versts. So, the caravan traveling along the first route had to cover a distance of 368 versts, and the caravan traveling along the second route had to cover a distance of 344 versts.

According to Herman Vamberi, the length of the caravan road used in Bukhara-Khiva trade relations was 60 miles, with facilities for stopping and drinking water every 5-10 miles. The camel caravan:

From Khiva to Khanka – 6 miles;

From Khanka to Shurakhona – 5 miles;

From Shurakhon to Akkamysch – 6 miles;

From Akkamysch to Tuyaboyi – 8 miles;

From Tuyaboyi to Tuyayuli – 10 miles;

From Yutsushak to Karakul – 10 miles;

From Karakul to Bukhara – covered the rocky road in 10-15 days.

The cost of transporting goods along the caravan route was around 1-1.5 gold coins per camel. The distance from Khiva to Bukhara was covered in 4-5 days on horseback. Waterways were also used to transport goods from Khiva to Bukhara by caravans. Initially, goods were brought from Khiva to Urgench, from where they were loaded onto ships on the Amu Darya and transported along the Amu Darya¹.

The goods brought to Chorjoi were loaded onto camels from here and transported to Karakul and through it to Bukhara². So, goods were transported from Khiva to Urgench on camels, from Urgench to Chorjoi on ships, and from Chorjoi to Bukhara (via Karakul) on camels again. In this direction, one Urgench batman (i.e. 2 poods 16 pounds)³ A fee of two coins was charged for transporting goods by water. When transporting goods by land from Urgench to Khiva, the carriers charged one coin for each camel load, and from Toshkhovuz to Khiva, seven coins for each camel load. Over short distances, loads were loaded and a fee of 5 to 10 coins was charged for transporting goods. When transporting goods by land from Khiva to Bukhara, a fee of 1-1.5 coins was charged for each camel load. If the camels belonged to Bukhara, they covered the road in 10 days, if the camels

¹ Неболсин Б.И. Очерки торговли России с странами Средней Азии Хивой, Бухарой Коканом. – СПб.: Б. и., 1856. – С. 169.

² Неболсин Б.И. Очерки торговли России с странами Средней Азии Хивой, Бухарой Коканом. – СПб.: Б. и., 1856. – С. 182-183.

³ Funt – ingliz o'lvov tizimida massa birligi, 0, 453 kg, 1/40 pud

of the Kyrgyz⁴ It took 15 or more days to travel the distance. It took 4-5 days to travel from Khiva to Bukhara on horseback. If there were draft horses, this journey could be completed in 3 days. When goods were transported from Bukhara to Khiva, the cost of transporting goods was the same, that is, it was equal to the cost of transporting goods from Khiva to Bukhara.⁵

The road connecting Bukhara and Khiva passed through the ruins of Kukertli. From here, goods were transported via Ilchik and Ust-yurt and sent by boats to Khanka⁶. From Ilchik or Ust-Yurt, the caravan route went through Bukhara to Samarkand, Jizzakh, and Tashkent, and its length was 970 versts. The main part of this route passed through populated areas, and along the way there were necessary conditions for the caravan to be supplied with water (wells with drinkable water). Of course, part of the route consisted of a waterway. 28 versts of the route between Amu Darya and Bukhara was sandy⁷.

Since the waterway was the main route in trade between the Bukhara Emirate and the Khiva Khanate, cargo was transported here by ships and boats along the Amu Darya. The route of loaded boats along the Amu Darya connected the cities of Kungirat, Charjoi, and Termez. At the beginning of the 20th century, 420 Khiva boats and 80 Bukhara boats were involved in trade between the Bukhara Emirate and the Khiva Khanate, and on average about 500,000 pounds of cargo were transported on them per year.⁸

In Bukhara-Khiva trade relations, the waterway (via the Amu Darya) was more advantageous for merchants than the caravan routes, as goods were delivered to Khiva or Bukhara faster and at lower cost. Goods sent to Bukhara were loaded onto boats in Urgench and brought to a destination a little further down from Chorjoi. From this destination, they were loaded onto camels supplied by Turkmen and arrived in Bukhara via Karakul in 2-3 days⁹.

About two thousand boats belonging to the inhabitants of the Khiva Khanate sailed from Kun'grat to Pitnak.¹⁰

The ability to transport goods on the Amu Darya was somewhat limited, and the boats that sailed on it did not have designated piers (stations). The movement of boats along the river was not specifically recorded. Usually, cargo boats were divided into 3 groups: 1) large boats - carrying goods from 2 thousand to 5 thousand pounds (from 32 tons to 80 tons); 2) medium boats - from 200 to 1 thousand pounds (from 3 tons to 16 tons); 3) small boats - boats carrying goods up to 200 pounds (from 3 tons to 200 kg.)¹¹.

Merchants had one or two boats and a ship, depending on their financial capabilities. Khiva was the main route across the river. Ships transported cargo to the other bank from the cities of

⁴ Bu yerda ikki o'rkachli tuyu nazarda tutilyapdi, bir o'rkachli tuyu tez yurgan, ikki o'rkachli tuyu nisbatan sekin yurgan.

⁵ ЎзР МДА И-1 фонд, 27-рўйхат, 926-иш, 14-варақ

⁶ ЎзР МДА И-1 фонд, 22-рўйхат, 832-иш, 23-варақ

⁷ ЎзР МДА И-1 фонд, 22-рўйхат, 832-иш, 9-варақ

⁸ Логофет Д.Н. Бухарское ханства под русским протекторатом. – СПб.: В.Березовский, 1911. – С. 212-213.

⁹ Неболсин. Торговые связи среднеазиатских владений между собою и караванние между ними сообщения. – С. 10 (Очерки торговли).

¹⁰ ЎзР МДА И-1 фонд, 22-рўйхат, 832-иш, 17-варақ

¹¹ Логофет Д.Н. Бухарское ханства под русским протекторатом. – СПб.: В.Березовский, 1911. – С. 212.

Kipchak, Khojaly, and Kungrad, opposite the cities of New Urgench and Gurlan, below the city of Yumur.¹²

In Khorezm, the Karamaz clan, an Uzbek clan, was engaged in boat building, and 6-7 craftsmen worked together to build one boat. Usually, boats were made of willow, and 80-85 pieces of willow were used to make one boat. It was not necessary to obtain official permission from the khan to build a boat, boats were mainly made according to the wishes of the customer.¹³

The size of the ships built varied, with a length of 10 fathoms being 2.5 fathoms wide and 1.5 fathoms high. There were also ships 12 fathoms long and over, capable of carrying up to 700 pounds of cargo. Such ships could carry 10 loaded camels or 100 people at a time. The ships were submerged in about one fathom of water¹⁴.

In the 19th century, the trade relations of the Bukhara and Kokand khanates played an important role in the economic life of the Central Asian region. Through internal trade, the khanates maintained socio-economic stability in their territories, while through foreign trade, they strengthened relations with other countries and promoted their political and economic interests. Trade relations with countries such as Russia, China, and Afghanistan strengthened the connection of the khanate's economy with the outside world.

Customs, taxes, and the rights of merchants played an important role in regulating trade relations. Measures aimed at ensuring the safety of caravan routes, expanding trade markets, and opening new routes had a positive impact on the development of trade.

Thus, the trade policies and relations of the Bukhara and Kokand Khanates had a profound impact not only on economic, but also on social and political relations between them and on the history of Central Asia as a whole. The experiences of this period also serve as an important historical source for studying contemporary trade and political strategies.

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¹³ ЎЗР МДА И-1 фонд, 22-рўйхат, 832-иш, 17-варақ

¹⁴ Зиёев Х. Ўрта Осиё ва Волга бўйлари. –Тошкент: Фан, 1965. –Б. 215

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